

IELTS SPEAKING

FURNITURE, HOMEAPPLIANCE
& ELECTRONIC DEVICES

同桌英语
PARTNER ENGLISH

Instruction: Self study & test (自学和自测)

- Please preview the vocabularies and sentence structures before the class and make sure you understand their meanings. (请同学课前预习词汇和句型, 确保清楚每个词汇, 搭配和句型的意思)
- Finish the exercise before the class and check the answers by yourself, it will help you understand the usage of the words and collocations. (请同学自学完词汇和句型之后完成练习并自行校对答案, 这对你理解它们的用法很有帮助哦!)
- Use the vocabularies and sentence structure as many as possible in your answer when practicing the topic questions in the class so that the teacher will help you check if you use them in a proper way or not. (在课堂上进行话题练习的时候, 尽可能多的使用这些单词, 短语, 搭配和句型, 老师会帮助你正确使用。)

VOCABULARY

FURNITURE, HOMEAPPLIANCE
& ELECTRONIC DEVICES

1. electronic devices
= electronic gadgets
2. a techie / technician
3. a technophobe
4. addictive
= to be addicted to
5. to crack the screen
6. functionality
7. portable

1. 电子设备
2. 技术人员
3. 技术恐惧者（不喜欢并害怕使用新技术的人）
4. 上瘾
5. 打破屏幕
6. 功能
7. 便携式的

8. antique furniture

9. contemporary furniture

10. flat-pack furniture

11. knobs

12. plenty of storage
space

13. full of clutter

14. minimalist

15. shabby-chic

8. 古董家具

9. 现代家具

10. 组装家具

11. 把手

12. 充足的储存空间

13. 乱七八糟的

14. 极简主义

15. 老旧但别致的

Exercise 1

plenty of storage space	minimalist	antique furniture	flat-pack furniture	shabby-chic
portable	crack its screen	techie	functionality	full of clutter

1. Those who keep on moving home should buy _____ because this kind of furniture is easy to disassemble and pack.
2. Real _____ costs a fortune. According to Time magazine, the most expensive ever sold is a cabinet. 3. _____ furniture is simple yet elegant furnishings that can help you save much space at home.
4. A desk cabinet has _____ where you can store your documents safely.
5. The _____ dining set adds a vintage touch to my uncle's home..
6. When buying gadgets, don't just consider the appearance—focus more on the _____.
7. Too much furnishings at home can make it look _____.
8. Dropping your smart phone multiple times will _____.
9. My sister has bought our grandpa a _____ tv, which he can take wherever he goes.
10. My boyfriend is a _____. Ask him anything about technology and he'll talk about it until your ears bleed.

USEFUL COLLOCATIONS

COLLOCATION	MEANING
To be a digital native	Young people who have an advantage because they have grown up with computers and mobile phones
To be computer literate	To be able to use a computer well
Cutting-edge technology	Up-to-date and the latest technology
Comfort over style	Comfort is more important to you than how fashionable a piece of furniture is
To cost an arm and a leg	To cost a lot of money
past its best	a bit old and tired

Exercise 2

cutting-edge

digital

past

comfort

literate

- 1. Even the older generation are computer _____ nowadays.
- 2. I like things to look nice, but when it comes to furniture I choose _____ over style.
- 3. My friend has just moved into a new apartment and it is full of _____ technology.
- 4. I know my sofa is _____ its best, but I love it.
- 5. Babies who are born at this age have the tendency to be _____ natives.

Exercise 3

labor-saving

shabby

time-saving

state-of-the-art

Most homes now are equipped with _____ appliances. These inventions undoubtedly bring comfort and convenience to us because they are _____ and _____. In addition to these creature comforts, various kinds of furniture are also found. They assist us in organizing our things and doing our daily activities like eating, watching TV, and finishing our work in front of a computer. Furthermore, it adorns our houses' interior ;however, it does the opposite thing when it becomes _____.

SENTENCE STRUCTURE

FURNITURE , HOMEAPPLIANCE & ELECTRONIC DEVICES

What is it?
a desk

If you are talking about a piece of furniture, think about all the different parts and what it is made of etc...

What are these?
drawers

What size is the desk - huge or medium-sized or tiny?
medium-sized

What is this?
a shelf

What is it made of?
It is made of wood

What colour are the doors?
They are dark grey

Are they glossy (光滑的) or matt (亚光的)?
They are glossy

What is this?
a cupboard

USEFUL SENTENCES/SENTENCE STARTERS FOR THIS TOPIC

<p>The first thing that comes to mind is...</p>	<p>I can't recall when I got it but...</p>	<p>I think it was roughly five years ago</p>	<p>I'm not entirely sure where I bought it from, but it was quite pricey (昂贵的) OR relatively cheap.</p>
<p>I'm a bit of a technophobe, but the one electronic gadget I love is my mobile.</p>	<p>Because we are now living in the computer age, everyone needs to be computer literate.</p>	<p>If I had to describe it in three words, I'd say it's... state-of-the-art, practical and addictive.</p>	<p>The most annoying thing is I'm always dropping it and I've cracked the screen several times.</p>
<p>For me, furniture needs to be comfort over style...</p>	<p>I prefer to buy antique furniture as it is usually better made than contemporary stuff.</p>	<p>If I had to describe it in three words, I'd say it's... shabby, worn, but irreplaceable (不可替代的).</p>	<p>In terms of furniture I'd say my style is shabby-chic (老旧但别致的).</p>

Homework answers

Exercise 1

plenty of storage space	minimalist	antique furniture	flat-pack furniture	shabby-chic
portable	crack its screen	techie	functionality	full of clutter

1. Those who keep on moving home should buy **flat-pack furniture** because this kind of furniture is easy to disassemble and pack.
2. Real **antique furniture** costs a fortune. According to Time magazine, the most expensive ever sold is a cabinet.
3. **Minimalist** furniture is simple yet elegant furnishings that can help you save much space at home.
4. A desk cabinet has **plenty of storage space** where you can store your documents safely.
5. The **shabby-chic** dining set adds a vintage touch to my uncle's home.
6. When buying gadgets, don't just consider the appearance—focus more on the **functionality**.
7. Too much furnishings at home can make it look **full of clutter**.
8. Dropping your smart phone multiple times will **crack its screen**.
9. My sister has bought our grandpa a **portable** TV, which he can take wherever he goes.
10. My boyfriend is a **techie**. Ask him anything about technology and he'll talk about it until your ears bleed.

Exercise 2

cutting-edge

digital

past

comfort

literate

- 1. Even the older generation are computer **literate** nowadays.
- 2. I like things to look nice, but when it comes to furniture I choose **comfort** over style.
- 3. My friend has just moved into a new apartment and it is full of **cutting-edge** technology.
- 4. I know my sofa is **past** its best, but I love it.
- 5. Babies who are born at this age have the tendency to be **digital** natives.

Exercise 3

labor-saving

shabby

time-saving

state-of-the-art

Most homes now are equipped with **state-of-the-art** appliances. These inventions undoubtedly bring comfort and convenience to us because they are **labor-saving** and **labor-saving**. In addition to these creature comforts, various kinds of furniture are also found. They assist us in organizing our things and doing our daily activities like eating, watching TV, and finishing our work in front of a computer. Furthermore, it adorns our houses' interior; however, it does the opposite thing when it becomes **shabby**.

English Partner

Hope you get a good score in the IELTS exam!